

SPARK PLASMA SINTERED HYDROXYAPATITE – ZIRCONIA COMPOSITES: STRUCTURAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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1 Introduction

Hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) (HAp) is a very attractive material for human tissue implantation, because it makes up ~69% of the weight of bone [1]. Unfortunately HAp possesses low mechanical properties (strength, fracture toughness), which is a barrier to its applications in load-bearing situations [2]. The mechanical properties of HAp composites, is based on the synthesis of composites and the second phase. As the second phase is yttria stabilized zirconia (ZrO_2) exhibits high toughness and has wide applications in bone surgery, because it is classified as a bioinert ceramic [3, 4]. Advanced sintering methods as spark plasma sintering (SPS) eliminated the regular problem, that during the sintering process HAp decomposed due to the applied high temperature [4]. SPS is capable for sintering ceramic powders fast to a high density at relatively low temperatures [4].

2 Experimental

The composites were prepared from two main materials; hydroxyapatite (HAp) and 8 mol% yttria stabilized zirconia. The submicron scale agglomerates of nano-scale primary particles HAp powder was made by reacting calcined eggshell and orthophosphoric acid, the details on the process were published in earlier work [5]. A commercial yttria stabilized zirconia (ZrO_2 -8mol% Y_2O_3) powder (Amdry 6643) was used in the as-provided state with 45 + 11 μm size particles. The composite was prepared by attritor milling (Union Process) for 2h to obtain a homogeneous mixture. The powders

were subsequently densified by the spark plasma sintering process on a Dr. Sinter SPS 7.40 MKVII system.

Powders were loaded on a graphite die (30 mm in diameter) and punch unit and heated to a predetermined temperature at a heating rate of 100°C/min, 30 MPa pressure was applied. The structure of composites was investigated by LEO 1540 XB scanning electron microscope (SEM) and by X-ray diffraction (XRD), using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The density of the samples was determined according to the Archimedes' principle. The microhardness of the composites were measured by Leitz Miniload 2 microhardness tester with an applied load of 4,903N and a holding time of 27s.

3 Results

3.1. Structural properties

SEM investigations of the HAp- ZrO_2 composites sintered at 800°C sintering temperature showed fine grain size and relative dense structure (Fig. 1 - 4).

Fig. 1. SEM images of pure HAp sintered at 800°C.

Fig. 2. SEM images of 95wt% HAp- 5wt% ZrO₂ composites sintered at 800°C.

Fig. 3. SEM images of 90wt% HAp- 10wt% ZrO₂ composites sintered at 800°C.

Fig. 4. SEM images of 60wt% HAp- 40wt% ZrO₂ composites sintered at 825°C.

The structure of composites (grain size 200-300nm) was preserved in the case of lower HAp content (60 wt%) and sintering temperature (825°C) (Fig. 4).

The relative density of the HAp-ZrO₂ composites sintered at 800°C as a function of their composition is shown in Tab. 1. Naturally the rate of the density is dependent on the composition. The composites with a composition of 90wt% HAp and 10wt % ZrO₂ showed a drastically density decreasing.

HAp (wt%)	ZrO ₂ (wt%)	Relative density (%)
100	0	90
95	5	96
90	10	85
60	40	94

Tab. 1. The relative density of the HAp-ZrO₂ composites sintered at 800°C.

Fig. 5. XRD analysis results of samples sintered at 800°C.

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Fig. 5. compares the XRD measurements at 800°C sintered composites with different ZrO₂ additions. Independent of the composition, HAp (JCPDS-PDF74-0565) and CaCO₃ (JCPDS-PDF 05-0586) phase was observed. The carbon inferential derived from the graphite die. In case of zirconia content composites the ZrO₂ (JCPDS-PDF01-089-9069) can be detected without any other elements, so the zirconia did not form compounds. The XRD results show that HAp phase can be maintained by the help of spark plasma sintering. Tri-calcium phosphates (TCP) were not formed in neither composites.

3.2. Mechanical properties

The microhardness of HAp-ZrO₂ composites sintered at 800°C are between 3 and 5,5 GPa. The composites consisting of zirconia indicated hardness high as (6-7 GPa). The rate of the hardness of the HAp-ZrO₂ composites was similar to the density results, which indicates that the microhardness is controlled by bonding among the grains in the sintered compacts.

The three point bending strength of pure HAp ceramic samples sintered at 800°C exhibited between 80 and 125 MPa. The 95wt%Hap 5wt% zirconia composites showed 99MPa bending strength. The 60wt% HAp and 40wt% ZrO₂ composite sintered at 825°C showed the highest bending strength, 125 MPa.

4 Conclusion

Nano hydroxyapatite-zirconia composites (Hap / ZrO₂) were studied. The Hap powder was reinforced with the bioinert yttria stabilized zirconia. The composites were prepared by fast and direct spark plasma sintering (SPS). During the SPS process low temperatures (800-825°C) were applied. The grain size of the sintered composites was observed between 200 and 1000 nm. The microhardness decreased with increasing bending strength. The structure of composites (grain size 200-300nm) was preserved in the case of lower HAp content (60 wt%) and sintering temperature (825°C). Any reaction between HAp and ZrO₂ was observed. It could be attributed to the very short time (5 minutes) and low sintering temperature of SPS.

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References

- [1] Y.W. Gu, N.H. Loh, K.A. Khor, S.B. Tor, P. Cheng "Spark plasma sintering of hydroxyapatite powders". *Biomaterials* Vol. 23, pp 37-43, 2002.
- [2] H. Guo, K. A. Khor, Y. Ch. Boey, X. Miao "Laminated and functionally graded hydroxyapatite/yttria stabilized tetragonal zirconia composites fabricated by spark plasma sintering". *Biomaterials* Vol. 24, pp. 667-675, 2003.
- [3] Y.-M. Kong, Ch.-J. Bea, S.-H. Lee, H.-W. Kim, H.-E. Kim "Improvement in biocompatibility of ZrO₂-Al₂O₃ nano-composite by addition of HA". *Biomaterials* Vol. 26, pp. 509-517, 2005.
- [4] X. Miao, Y. Chen, H. Guo, K. A. Khor "Spark plasma sintered hydroxyapatite-yttria stabilized zirconia composites". *Cer. Int.* Vol. 1 30, pp. 1793-1796, 2004.
- [5] G. Gergely, F. Wéber, I. Lukács, L. Illés, A. L. Tóth, Z. E. Horváth, J. Mihály, Cs. Balázs "Nano hydroxyapatite preparation from biogenic raw materials". *Cent. Eur. J. Chem.* Vol. 8, Nr. 2, pp. 375-381, 2010